

Teaching Strategies in Engineering to Improve the Educational Conditions of Neurodivergent Students

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This study investigates teaching strategies that may later be implemented in engineering programs, in the context of a current interest in increasing inclusion in the classrooms of future professionals. The main objective focuses on analyzing already-used and functional strategies applied in other universities at the international level, to adapt them to engineering programs. A quantitative methodological design was used through the implementation of a Likert scale applied to a sample of 30 students from the Industrial Civil Engineering program at Universidad Arturo Prat. The instrument consisted of 15 statements where respondents expressed agreement, disagreement, or lack of knowledge about the statements presented. The results revealed indications of a high level of acceptance and inclusion within the institution, both among instructors and students, regarding the use of digital tools and support materials for neurodivergent students. However, there are still shortcomings in the adaptation of physical spaces and evaluation models. On the other hand, the results support the need to continue improving classroom environments and assessment methods for students with cognitive diversity, as previous studies highlight the importance of adapting these elements to increase the retention and graduation rates of neurodivergent students. Finally, the field under study still needs to continue growing, and thanks to the current emphasis on inclusion, this progress is achievable. Implementing strategies helps bring visibility to explore new horizons and better prepare educational institutions to face the challenge of diversity within classrooms and even beyond.

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1. INTRODUCTION

In a constantly evolving world, and particularly after the profound changes triggered by the Covid-19 pandemic, higher education institutions face unprecedented challenges in training future professionals with neurodiversity. In this new era, where the need to feel understood and represented has become paramount, universities bear the responsibility of creating safe and inclusive spaces for neurologically diverse individuals.

As stated in [1], promoting inclusive education that recognizes and values neurodivergence not only enriches the learning environment but also prepares all students to face a diverse and complex world. This challenge demands a profound adaptation of teaching methods, as well as the development of specific strategies that guarantee authentic understanding and comprehensive support.

The inclusion of neurodivergent individuals in professional training is not merely an objective but a crucial necessity for building a more equitable and representative future.

As noted in [2]:

Inclusive education directed at students with functional diversity presents a social and environmental approach that considers two converging factors: the capacity of the student and the environment in which they develop; therefore, it is fundamental that the educational system adapts to the student, and not the student to the conditions of the system.

This approach maintains that the educational system should adapt to the needs of the student rather than expecting students to conform to a rigid environment. By generating a more welcoming and receptive environment for the university community, diversity is recognized, and the multiplicity of approaches to addressing challenges in academic life is valued. In addition, this approach benefits the student during their training and prepares future professionals with the necessary competencies to function in an increasingly inclusive and diverse labor market.

In [3], it is mentioned that engineering education must recognize and value the diversity of identities and experiences—including students with Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD)—to foster an inclusive learning environment that benefits everyone. This perspective highlights the importance of research focused on inclusion, arguing that the benefits are not limited solely to neurodivergent individuals.

Thus, the entire educational community, including external actors, benefits by cultivating a positive perception of an inclusive environment, strengthening the image of academic institutions as open and equitable spaces. This research addresses the needs of students with neurodiversity while also contributing significant value to the educational community as a whole, promoting a culture of respect and understanding that transcends academic boundaries.

This study seeks to analyze strategies that may later be implemented in educational environments, specifically in engineering programs. To achieve this, the research focuses on the following specific objectives: analyzing educational strategies already implemented in various universities worldwide regarding the inclusion of neurodivergent students in classrooms; describing the pedagogical strategies that have shown the best results; comparing the strategies implemented in different engineering fields; and evaluating how the implementation of these strategies has impacted the academic performance of students with neurodiversity.

According to [3], the low number of responses directly connecting diversity or inclusion with engineering... could indicate a critical gap that must be addressed in engineering education. This observation underscores the need to address this gap to ensure a more inclusive and effective educational environment.

The hypotheses proposed in this study are as follows: Universities in Chile, as well as those abroad, have pedagogical strategies already implemented and functional concerning the education of neurodivergent students; the educational strategies that have produced the best results focus exclusively on how to include neurodivergent students; in the field of engineering, there should not be major differences among its

branches, since it is a discipline currently in the process of incorporating inclusion and equity strategies; thanks to the implementation of these teaching strategies, the academic performance of neurodivergent students has increased significantly.

2. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

The following section outlines the fundamental concepts that will guide the development of the research, focusing on the definition, study, description, analysis, and comparison of various teaching strategies aimed at neurodivergent students. Inclusive pedagogical approaches will be addressed to adapt the learning process to the individual needs of these students, promoting their effective participation in the classroom. Furthermore, prior experiences and empirical studies evaluating the implementation of these strategies in different educational contexts will be examined, analyzing the results obtained in terms of impact on academic performance, social integration, and emotional well-being.

2.1 Basic Concepts

According to [4], a teaching strategy is defined as the procedures or resources used by the teaching agent to promote meaningful learning. This implies that strategies are tools that instructors employ to facilitate student learning, focusing on the design, planning, development, and execution of learning content, whether orally or in writing. These strategies are fundamental in the educational process as they focus on the transmission of information while actively engaging students in their own learning process.

According to [5,6], meaningful learning is the acquisition of new knowledge that has relevance, understanding, critical thinking, and the ability to be used in explanations, arguments, and problem-solving situations. Meaningful learning requires both that the learner adopt a meaningful learning attitude and that the material to be learned be potentially meaningful for him or her. It is an approach that seeks to ensure that students acquire information, understand it, and can apply it effectively in life and new situations. New knowledge is integrated coherently and meaningfully with the student's prior knowledge.

This type of learning is characterized by:

- Understanding and Meaning
- Interaction with Prior Knowledge
- Progressivity and Complexity
- Positive Affective Experiences

Neurodivergence is considered a variation in neurological functioning that includes conditions such as autism, Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder, and dyslexia, among others. Neurodivergence also implies recognizing the challenges that neurodivergent individuals face in their social and educational development. An approach is proposed that values these differences while advocating for changes and adaptations in society—including academic libraries—to facilitate inclusion and access to education for all students [7].

According to [8], neurodivergence is a concept that includes individuals with mental processing that diverges from the norm, in contrast to neurotypical individuals, whose processing falls within the norm. It is noted that neurodiversity includes both neurotypical and neurodivergent individuals, and it is emphasized that it is impossible to speak of a single type of normal cognitive processing since multiple cognitive patterns coexist and may vary throughout an individual's life.

2.2 Analysis of Implemented Teaching Strategies

According to [9], the School Integration Program (PIE) in Chile implements various teaching strategies to support students with Autism Spectrum Disorder and other special educational needs. Some of these include:

- Collaboration among teachers: Promoting collaboration between regular teachers and special education teachers, as well as the involvement of specialists such as psychologists, speech therapists, and therapists.
- Psychological support: Providing strong psychological support that complements academic aspects and helps students manage their emotions and behaviors.
- Educational materials and resources: Using various educational materials and human resources to facilitate learning.
- Training: Offering training for teachers to implement appropriate pedagogical strategies for students with special educational needs.

Curricular management: Making curricular adaptations to address the specific needs of students.

In another study presented by [10], several teaching strategies are highlighted that are used exclusively to support students with Autism Spectrum Disorder. These strategies aim to help educators better understand how ASD students learn in order to implement pedagogical practices that facilitate both academic and personal success. Some include:

- Celebration of Knowledge: Encouraging students to share their knowledge about topics of interest and using that knowledge as a resource in the classroom.
- Learning Ladder: Contextualizing tasks based on student interests, providing scaffolding and differentiated tasks to adapt to their abilities.
- Focus on Cognitive Diversity: Recognizing the variety of abilities among students —both gifted and disabled— and adapting teaching strategies to their needs.
- Professional Development: Offering training for educators to adopt a strengths-based approach when working with autistic students, valuing their uniqueness.

Additionally, according to [11], higher education plays a key role in promoting diversity and inclusion, especially regarding neurodiversity. To support neurodivergent students and ensure their academic success, it is crucial to implement appropriate strategies such as:

- Environment of Acceptance and Support: Creating an inclusive environment by raising awareness among staff and students, promoting empathy so that everyone feels valued.
- Personalization and Flexibility: Offering personalized support with curricular adaptations, flexible deadlines, and additional resources, allowing each student to progress at their own pace.
- Open Communication and Collaboration: Encouraging effective communication among students, educators, and support staff to ensure needs are heard and individualized plans are developed.

Furthermore, it is emphasized that the responsibility of supporting these students lies not only with institutions but also with the State, which must establish adequate policies and resources. Inclusion is an ongoing process that brings enormous benefits by creating a more equitable educational environment where each student can thrive academically and professionally.

2.3 Strategies That Have Shown the Best Results

According to [12], one of the strategies that showed the best results was flexibility and the possibility of choice in learning, which allowed neurodivergent students to work at their own pace and collaborate

effectively on tasks. Although some students initially felt overwhelmed by this flexibility, formative feedback and collaborative work fostered confidence and strengthened their skills.

Additionally, the implementation of the Learning Ladder, as explained in [11], also proved to be highly effective. This model enables teachers to adapt their pedagogical approaches to the individual needs of students with Autism Spectrum Disorder, allowing them to excel in tasks that utilize their cognitive strengths—such as memorization— while receiving additional support in areas that present greater challenges, such as conceptual understanding. Both strategies significantly contributed to improved academic performance and promoted an inclusive environment that enhances emotional well-being and social integration.

2.4 Comparison of Strategies in Different Engineering Fields

Regarding the strategies proposed and used by [12], the study compared how these would be applied in Industrial Civil Engineering, spanning basic sciences, engineering sciences, and specialization areas within this degree. The strategies were compared across the various branches as follows:

- Avoid assuming bad intentions: Teachers should investigate the reasons behind the lack of participation or incomplete assignments instead of assuming disinterest. Offering tutoring and fostering an environment where students feel safe to express questions without fear of judgment is essential.
- Flexibility and options: Allowing students to choose between different methods and approaches to problem-solving adapts to their learning styles and encourages engagement.
- Creating an inclusive environment: Encouraging small-group discussions and using online learning platforms helps students feel comfortable sharing ideas and questions.
- Facilitating compassionate discussions: Rather than correcting immediately, teachers can guide students with questions that lead them to problem resolution, promoting deeper learning and open dialogue about ethical dilemmas.
- Providing clarity in expectations: Using clear rubrics and examples of previous work helps students understand evaluation criteria and what is expected of them in projects.
- Use of technology and learning tools: Implementing online simulations and modeling software in science and engineering courses facilitates the understanding of complex concepts and improves collaboration in projects.

Inclusive learning strategies in industrial engineering allow students to develop critical skills essential in today's workforce. By offering flexibility in participation and adaptive assessment options, students learn to collaborate effectively in diverse teams, reflecting the reality of many modern organizations. This adaptability not only fosters a more equitable learning environment but also prepares students to address complex problems from multiple perspectives—an indispensable skill in the industry.

2.5 Impact of the Implementation of These Strategies

The strategies implemented in the School Integration Program, according to [9], have various impacts, although the results have not been entirely positive. According to the article, the following impacts are observed regarding the situation of students with special educational needs (SEN):

- Permanence in the school system: An 8% decrease has been observed in the retention of students with special educational needs, indicating that many are unable to remain in the system, revealing a challenge in the program's effectiveness.

- Improvements in learning: The percentage of students showing improvement has dropped from 51% to 37%, suggesting that most are not experiencing the expected academic gains.
- Emotional and social support: Although it is recognized that psychological support and collaboration among teachers and specialists can improve students' emotional and social well-being, specific data are not provided.
- Curricular adaptations: Adaptations have been made in curricular management and the use of educational materials to meet the needs of students with ASD and other SEN. Although the positive impact is not quantified, these adaptations are essential for individualized learning.

Overall, although the strategies of the PIE are designed to improve inclusion and learning among students with special needs, the results indicate that there are still significant challenges to be addressed in order to achieve a more positive and lasting impact on their education.

3. METHOD

The methodology used in this study was the quantitative approach, which, according to [13], aims in quantitative research to generalize the results found in a specific group to a larger population. The main goal of quantitative studies is the formulation and demonstration of theories and the second methodology. Finally, the data collection instrument used was a survey based on the Likert scale.

The design of this study is a cross-sectional design, also known as a cross-sectional research design, which is a type of research design used to observe and analyze a phenomenon at a specific moment in time. In this approach, data are collected from different subjects or groups at a single point in time, allowing researchers to examine the relationship between variables and obtain a snapshot of the situation under study.

This design is useful for identifying patterns and correlations, but it does not allow for establishing causal relationships due to the lack of longitudinal follow-up, according to [14].

According to [15], who address the descriptive methodological design in the context of Descriptive Analysis, they highlight its relevance as a strategy for handling information in qualitative research. It is mentioned that descriptive analysis allows the visibility of the referents considered relevant during data collection and processing, thus facilitating the transformation of observations into manageable data.

3.1 Instrument

The survey structure consists of fifteen statements, carefully designed to avoid any bias or predisposition in participants' responses. Each statement uses a five-point Likert scale, where values represent the degree to which respondents agree or disagree with the statement: (1) Completely Disagree, (2) Disagree, (3) Neither Agree nor Disagree, (4) Agree, and (5) Completely Agree. This scale allows for a clear and quantifiable measurement of perceptions. Its objective is to evaluate the opinions of the Arturo Prat University community regarding the inclusion of neurodivergent students in the academic environment.

3.2 Participants

To ensure the statistical validity of the results, it was determined that the minimum number of respondents should be 30 people, ultimately obtaining a total of 32 surveyed individuals. This sample size allows for the identification of trends and key points in perceptions regarding inclusion, guiding how the university community perceives and addresses challenges related to neurocognitive diversity.

3.3 Procedure

In order to determine the level of appreciation of neurodivergent students in university classrooms, the survey was administered to the sample only once. Based on this information, a reliability analysis was conducted by calculating Cronbach's alpha of the survey, and the results were analyzed through bar graphs.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results obtained from this study, which have been carefully analyzed and reflect the key findings derived from the research.

4.1 Reliability Analysis

The internal consistency analysis indicated that Cronbach's alpha was 0.81, which suggests that the instrument has high reliability.

4.2 Descriptive Analysis

This section presents the results obtained in the descriptive analysis through bar graphs that summarize respondents' opinions per item in each survey. Below are the graphs by question.

In Figure 1, the majority of respondents, specifically 39.4%, show a neutral position toward the statement about the adaptation of materials by instructors to different learning styles. Following this, a trend toward disagreement is presented; some consider that efforts are made in this area, while others do not perceive such adaptation. This may indicate an opportunity for improvement regarding inclusive learning strategies in the Industrial Civil Engineering program at Arturo Prat University.

Figure 1. Adaptation of materials used in the classroom

In Figure 2, the most frequent response was disagreement with 39.4%; these results reflect that students perceive a lack of diversity in evaluation methods, which may suggest challenges for those with different learning needs. This observation highlights the importance of developing flexible assessments that facilitate inclusion and aim to achieve equitable performance for neurodivergent students in the Industrial Civil Engineering program at Arturo Prat University.

Figure 2. Adaptive evaluation formats

In Figure 3, 36.4% of respondents adopt a neutral position regarding the accessibility of reading and study materials in alternative formats. This indicates that availability is perceived, but there remains some uncertainty regarding accessibility, suggesting that materials for the Industrial Civil Engineering program at

Arturo Prat University could continue to expand in availability and formats to better meet the diverse needs of neurodivergent students.

Figure 3. Accessible materials and alternative formats

In Figure 4, the predominant neutral response, corresponding to 57.6% of respondents, regarding the level of instructors' knowledge about neurodivergent differences, suggests that participants do not perceive whether teachers are informed on this subject. This reflects a lack of visibility of the knowledge that instructors may have concerning neurodivergence, highlighting a potential area for improvement in the Industrial Civil Engineering program in terms of inclusive education.

Figure 4. Instructors' knowledge level regarding neurodivergent differences

In Figure 5, the most common response was disagreement with 45.5%, followed by complete disagreement. This indicates that respondents perceive that the physical classroom environment is not adequately adapted to reduce sensory distractions. This suggests that factors such as noise or room layout affect the concentration of students with specific sensory needs. This highlights an opportunity to improve physical spaces, contributing to a more accessible learning environment for all.

Figure 5. Adaptation of the physical classroom environment

In Figure 6, agreement predominates with 45.5%, concerning the promotion of an environment of respect for cognitive differences in the classroom. Respondents suggest that, in general, instructors and students in the Industrial Civil Engineering program at Arturo Prat University value and respect cognitive differences — an essential aspect for fostering inclusion.

Figure 6. Promotion of an environment of respect for cognitive differences

In Figure 7, the most frequent choice is agreement (54.5%), which reflects a positive perception among respondents regarding the encouragement of active participation in the classroom, regardless of abilities.

Both instructors and the educational environment of the Industrial Civil Engineering program at Arturo Prat University support equal participation —an encouraging result, as it implies an effort to involve all students. Maintaining and strengthening these inclusive practices contributes to an equitable educational experience.

In Figure 8, the balanced distribution of responses among disagreement, neutrality, and agreement regarding flexibility in class pacing suggests a varied perception among respondents. While some perceive efforts toward adapting the pace, others believe it is insufficient or not evident. This indicates inconsistency in the application of flexible teaching methods, which is detrimental, as adapting the teaching pace would contribute to a more inclusive and accessible environment for all, including those with neurodivergence.

Figure 7. Encouraging active participation of all students

Figure 8. Use of flexible class pacing

In Figure 9, the neutral response of 45.5% regarding the availability of individualized support for neurodivergent students suggests that respondents do not have a clear perception of the existence of such support. To improve the educational experience of neurodivergent students, it would be beneficial to more effectively promote and communicate individualized support options.

Figure 9. Individualized support for neurodivergent students

In Figure 10, the variety of responses ranging from disagreement to neutrality and agreement indicates diverse perceptions regarding the use of multisensory teaching techniques in the classroom. While some feel these methods are employed in their education, others do not perceive them in the same way or consider them insufficient.

Figure 10. Use of multisensory teaching techniques

In Figure 11, the distribution of responses ranging from complete disagreement to neutrality represents a predominantly negative perception regarding the design of exams and evaluations based on different cognitive abilities. This indicates a belief that evaluations do not adapt to the diversity of skills and learning styles present in the classroom. Such findings reflect the need to adapt assessment methods to be more inclusive and equitable so that neurodivergent students have the opportunity to demonstrate their knowledge and abilities.

Figure 11. Design of exams and evaluations

In Figure 12, the predominant response of 48.5% is neither agree nor disagree, indicating that respondents have mixed perceptions regarding the promotion of collaboration and teamwork adapted to neurodivergent students' abilities. While some perceive efforts by instructors to foster an inclusive environment, others are not fully satisfied with the effectiveness of these practices. The teaching staff could benefit from training in various teamwork strategies that recognize and adapt to neurodiversity.

Figure 12. Promotion of collaboration and teamwork

In Figure 13, the predominant neutral response of 45.5% indicates that respondents have an unclear perception regarding access to academic advising tailored to the needs of neurodivergent students. This implies that while some perceive available resources and support, others do not have clarity regarding accessibility or adequacy. Strengthening this aspect by implementing strategies to provide personalized academic advising ensures that neurodivergent students understand and benefit from available support options.

Figure 13. Access to academic advising for neurodivergent students

In Figure 14, most responses range from agree, completely agree, to neutral, indicating a positive perception regarding flexibility in course design to allow different ways of demonstrating knowledge. This reveals that the program is adopting an inclusive approach that values diversity. Nonetheless, to strengthen this effort, it is helpful to maintain communication about available options and consider expanding additional evaluation modalities.

Figure 14. Flexible course design to demonstrate knowledge

In Figure 15, the distribution of responses—including neutrality, agreement, and complete agreement—indicates a positive perception among respondents regarding the accessibility and ease of navigation of online resources for those with cognitive differences. This suggests that, overall, the digital resources used in the Industrial Civil Engineering program at Arturo Prat University are well designed. However, the presence of neutral responses also indicates areas for improvement in usability or accessibility.

Figure 15. Accessible and easy-to-navigate online resources

5. CONCLUSIONS

This research examined teaching strategies that can improve the educational conditions of neurodivergent students in higher education, particularly in engineering programs, to analyze strategies that may subsequently be implemented in the educational field, especially in the area mentioned. In addition, strategies implemented in both foreign and Chilean institutions were analyzed; those that yielded the best results were described, and strategies already implemented in different branches of engineering were compared to later evaluate their impact. Throughout the study, it was concluded that, in Chile—specifically at Arturo Prat University and in the Industrial Civil Engineering program—there is intention and motivation to be inclusive in classroom settings; however, there is a deficit in applying methodologies and strategies related to examinations, individualized support for students, and the delivery of knowledge to neurodivergent students.

At the global level and in the country's capital, part of their strategies is based on collaboration and teacher training, with support in the professional development of neurodivergent students, offering various educational materials and resources to facilitate learning. These points confirm our first hypothesis: Chilean and foreign institutions have implemented and functional pedagogical strategies, such as the current PIE program. However, the hypothesis stating that the most successful strategies focus exclusively on including neurodivergent students is not confirmed, as, for example, the Learning Ladder strategy does not focus on including the student but rather on adapting instructors to their needs. Moreover, students themselves identify the type of learning that facilitates their learning, deviating from the concept of solely social, including the student.

Regarding the third hypothesis, which proposes inclusion in engineering fields, the research results demonstrate that this issue is not exclusive to engineering; rather, it is part of a global trend toward inclusion in higher education. Many strategies originate in teaching programs, where practices centered on diverse learning are developed. The mentioned strategies are highly adaptable and applicable across various academic contexts, including technical disciplines such as engineering.

Their implementation has been effective due to their user-friendly and practical approach, facilitating integration across different fields. The hypothesis is confirmed by showing that inclusive strategies, although developed in other areas, can be successfully adopted in engineering, promoting a more inclusive environment and enhancing the performance of neurodivergent students. However, in terms of academic performance, no improvement has been observed, with performance decreasing from 51% to 37%. This refutes the fourth hypothesis, which suggests that the implementation of these strategies helped improve the performance of neurodivergent students; this reflects that most of these students are not benefiting from these strategies.

The most important findings obtained from the survey conducted at Arturo Prat University highlight that there is a high level of acceptance and inclusion toward neurodivergent students from both students and instructors, as well as easy accessibility to support materials. However, there is no adaptation of the physical environment in which classes are delivered, and no effort is observed in designing evaluations and exams aligned with the needs of students with ASD. In contrast, Valle (2022), in the context of teaching Basic Biomedical Sciences to undergraduate students, concludes that the main strategies must focus on the need for inclusion and the transformation of educational paradigms, adaptation of evaluations, training, and the proposal of didactic strategies to develop and apply specific methods that ensure access, retention, and completion of studies for neurodivergent students.

The research faced limitations due to a small sample size and limited information on the topic studied, as it is an issue that has only gained visibility in the past decade. This leads us to consider that the topic in question should be addressed in future research and educational-level discussions, taking advantage of the visibility it has gained today. An increasingly inclusive world requires not only that students and teachers know, consider, and apply their knowledge to include neurodivergent students, but also that society as a whole begins to assign them the importance they deserve. Could the strategies studied be implemented in non-educational areas as well? Are there more ways to include these students in classrooms? Has sufficient importance been given to this topic today?

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